

Deep Learning Classification of Colon Polyps for Colorectal Cancer Detection (CRC) Using Feature-Enhanced *Ex Vivo* Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) Images

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ABSTRACT

Colorectal cancer (CRC) is a leading cause of cancer deaths, with thousands of new cases each year worldwide. CRCs mainly develop from dysplastic polyps, which gradually progress into malignancies. Population-based screening with colonoscopy is a crucial cancer prevention strategy, potentially decreasing CRC mortality by up to 57%. Despite its effectiveness, colonoscopy can be improved. Recent efforts to enhance colonoscopic efficiency tried to reduce the procedure time and cost by leaving diminutive polyps (<5 mm) in place. However, such a strategy introduces additional risks since it implies leaving 80% of the, now-resected, polyps in place. Thus, technological advancements are needed to minimize the risk from unresected polyps. OCT can aid in detecting and classifying colon polyps, but its application in colon imaging lags behind other clinical uses due to its dependence on images of tissue microstructure without any biochemical information, necessary, to distinguish early signs of cancer. This study proposes a novel approach to overcome limitations in interpreting OCT images for CRC screening. *Ex vivo* OCT images of colon polyps were used to extract features that remain unused and indicate sub-resolution and biochemical tissue changes, such as scatterer size and group velocity dispersion. Along with the intensity images, feature images were created and used for deep learning (DL) classification with late fusion to distinguish benign (normal and hyperplastic) from malignant (adenoma and SSA) polyps. The novel DL method resulted in 88.3 % correct classification rate per image.

1. INTRODUCTION

CRC is a leading cause of cancer deaths, with over 356,000 new cases in Europe in 2023. [1]. CRCs mainly develop from dysplastic polyps (adenomas) that gradually evolve into malignancies. Population-based screening is an important prevention strategy, potentially reducing CRC mortality by 18% to 57%. [2]. Since 2003, the EU has recommended CRC screening for individuals aged 50-74 years. [3]. Sedated colonoscopy accounts for most CRC screenings, contributing to a 35% decrease in CRC mortality over the past two decades [4]. However, the rate of CRC incidence has increased by 8% over the last decade [5], raising the number of required colonoscopies. Although effective, colonoscopy screening can be improved [6]-[8]. Recent efforts to enhance colonoscopic efficiency aim to decrease procedure time, pathology load, and costs by leaving diminutive polyps (<5 mm) in place. A successful "leave-in-situ" strategy could save millions of euros [9]. However, this creates risks by leaving 80% of currently resected polyps in place. Therefore, technological advancements are important to reduce the risk from unresected polyps. OCT offers a non-invasive solution for early CRC detection and classification with minimum patient inconvenience. It can be performed on a sedated patient with minimal effort. Yet, colon OCT is still behind other clinical applications due to the absence of appropriate endoscopic systems for imaging its large, corrugated anatomy [10]. Moreover, the diagnosis is based on the OCT images of tissue microstructure and heuristic "radiological-like" criteria, without the functional or biochemical information necessary to detect early signs of cancer [11]. Studies have extracted various features from OCT images, such as intensity and texture-based features, to address this issue. Recently, OCT data were used to identify characteristics that produced biomarkers related to tissue abnormalities. These unique properties, reflecting biochemical alterations of disease, include group velocity dispersion, scatterer size (similar to cell nucleus size), and refractive index [12–17]. In this study, *ex vivo* OCT images of human polyps from patients undergoing colonoscopy were acquired and processed using a fully automated algorithm for image segmentation and feature extraction. Feature-enhanced OCT images were created by overlaying the values of most significant features onto the intensity OCT images. These enhanced images utilized in a novel deep learning method with late fusion to distinguish benign (normal and hyperplastic) from malignant (adenoma and SSA) polyps.

2. METHODOLOGY

A. The Dataset

The OCT data for this project were collected using a Fourier domain OCT system, with a center wavelength of 1310 nm, an axial resolution of 14 μm and an A-Scan rate of 100 kHz. The data were collected at the Massachusetts General Hospital. One hundred and seventeen volunteers were enrolled in the study. The imaging took place in the colonoscopy suite and the data were acquired immediately after resection of the polyp. Subsequently, histological H&E sections and diagnosis

were also be provided. The dataset included 117 patients with various histopathologic diagnosis. *En face* images were used to outline the extend of the polyp in the imaging volume as well as areas of histology-confirmed diagnosis (normal, hyperplastic, adenoma, serrated lesion) to be used as the ground truth. The marking was performed manually by a trained histopathologist (Fig. 1A).

B. Image Processing and Feature Extraction

Each B-Scan image that was assigned a diagnosis was automatically segmented to retrieve the top portion of the colon image (Fig. 1B). Segmentation was performed by thresholding followed by a series of morphological operations to remove small regions due to noise and vertical and horizontal lines due to artifact. The top surface was identified and the section between the top surface and 150 μm below was segmented (Fig. 1C).

Several features were extracted from each neighborhood of each image, including: (i) First-order intensity statistics: Ten features of the intensity distribution, such as mean, standard deviation, variance, skewness, median, kurtosis, min, max, and mode. (ii) Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM): Four main GLCM features (correlation, contrast, homogeneity, and energy) calculated for three different offsets (1, 3 and 5). (iii) Novel feature – Group Velocity Dispersion (GVD): Measured using the speckle degradation technique. Changes in GVD, can indicate biochemical changes caused by disease [13]. (iv) Novel feature – scatterer size (SS): Mean SS estimated using Mie Theory and the bandwidth of the correlation of the derivative (COD) of the OCT spectrum from a frequency transformation [14]. (v) Fractal Dimension (FD): Calculated using the box counting method from predefined neighborhoods of each image [18]. Each feature was estimated over an 11x11 pixel neighborhood (55x55 μm). First and second order intensity and fractal features were calculated for both logarithmic and non-logarithmic intensity. The feature values were overlaid over the intensity OCT image as a color value in an HSV image, where hue (H) represented the value of the feature and value (V) was the intensity of the OCT structural image. The saturation (S) was set to 1 everywhere (Fig.1 D &E). All the images were normalized to the same color range to ensure good contrast and make the results comparable.

Figure 1. Error! Bookmark not defined.(A) En face projection of a polyp created from a volume of 1000 OCT images (each 1000 A-Scans x 1024 pixels). The brown line marks the polyp's extent, while the green and red lines show normal and adenomatous sections, respectively. (B) Image section corresponding to the green dashed line in A. The green lines show the automatically segmented region (150 μm). (C) Segmented section from B. (D) Segmented section resulted from the red area in A. (E) Features calculated over each 11x11 pixel neighborhood of the above image. The value of each feature is represented by the color (H) over the intensity (V) of the original OCT image, in HSV format.

C. Deep Learning Classification with Late Fusion

First, the extracted features, from individual neighborhoods, were ranked using 3 different methods (MRMR, Chi Square and t-test) and an overall ranking was calculated for each. Enhanced OCT images were created using the values of the top-ranking features in each category. The number of features used was selected by successively adding more features that increased the algorithm's performance. An exhaustive evaluation of all possible combinations was not performed due time constrains. The images were classified as benign (normal and hyperplastic) vs. malignant potential (adenoma and sessile serrated adenoma). Data augmentation was implemented by applying a set of augmentation operations (i.e. translation and rotation) to the original images during training. A pre-trained ResNet18 neural network was utilized, modifying the last layers to incorporate a fully connected layer for two-class classification, and finally the classification layer. Each dataset of feature-enhanced images was classified using a separate network and Leave-Ten-Patients-Out (L10PO) cross-validation. Late fusion was performed by creating a new feature vector for each image by combining the classification scores of each different dataset. A conventional classifier using linear discriminant analysis (LDA) was applied to produce a final classification of each image (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Training flow of the proposed deep learning method with late fusion. Each feature dataset passes through a separate ResNet18 neural network, and the scores are combined into a feature vector which is then passed as the input to a traditional machine learning classifier (LDA) to produce the final result.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

For the purposes of an initial classification, to serve as a baseline reference before the application of the proposed DL method, the standard intensity images were used first. The intensity images (normalized and logged in gray scale) were fed to a ResNet18. The results showed 85.5% classification accuracy with 88.4% sensitivity and 79.6% specificity. Feature-enhanced OCT images, created from the twenty-one most significant features, were selected. Those included: six first order intensity statistics, six GLCM features, four fractal statistics and five spectral related features. The images were, initially, classified separately, resulting in accuracy ranging from 79.2% to 83.4%, sensitivity from 82.9% to 88.1%, and specificity from 65.8% to 76.0%. After late fusion of the score vectors from the original intensity dataset and the feature-enhanced OCT images, the performance was improved, resulting in 88.3% accuracy, 93.5% sensitivity, 77.9% specificity, and an AUC of 0.857.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The use of features extracted from the OCT intensity images as well as the speckle and spectral content of each neighborhood shows great promise for the classification of colon polyps. With an accuracy of 88.3 % per image with L10PO cross-validation, the proposed methodology is very promising and warrants further research to increase the number of patients included as well as further refine the algorithms and increase the robustness of the approach. This level of performance would be invaluable in enabling the use of OCT for leave-in-situ applications. With future developments, this method can offer significant improvements in the accuracy of endoscopic OCT imaging and its application in colon polyp management.

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